

Evaluating weather and climate information services for heat and drought adaptation in Southeast Europe: gaps, opportunities and design principles

Spyridon Paparrizos^a, Dragan Milošević^b, Zorica Podračanin^c, Tim Friso Lodewijk^a, Raffaele Vignola^a, Samuel J. Sutanto^a, Maria del Pozo Garcia^a, Wouter J. Smolenaars^a, Miroslav Vujičić^d, Gordana Kranjac-Berisavljevic^e, Biljana Basarin^d

^a *Water Systems and Global Change, Wageningen University and Research, P.O. Box 47, 6700 AA Wageningen, the Netherlands*

^b *Meteorology and Air Quality, Wageningen University and Research, P.O. Box 47, 6700 AA Wageningen, the Netherlands*

^c *Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

^d *Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

^e *WACWISA, University for Development Studies, Mepukada, Tamale, Ghana*

HIGHLIGHTS

- Assessed Weather & Climate Information Services (WCIS) for heat and drought adaptation in Southeast Europe.
- Identified key design and communication gaps hindering WCIS effectiveness.
- Applied mixed-methods: literature review, surveys, and interviews.
- Proposed design principles to improve WCIS usability and trust.
- Highlighted need for sector-specific, user-friendly WCIS for adaptation.

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ABSTRACT

Although many Weather and Climate Information Services are available in Southeast Europe, their contribution to enhancing long-term climate resilience remains unclear. This study evaluates the role of WCIS in supporting climate change adaptation in SEE with regard to extreme heat and drought events, and identifies key gaps. In this study, heat and drought refer to perceived conditions of elevated temperature and prolonged precipitation deficit as understood by stakeholders, rather than strictly defined meteorological thresholds. The analysis draws on a mixed-methods approach combining bibliometric and market analysis, surveys, and semi-structured interviews, with results reflecting predominantly qualitative, perception-based insights. Findings highlight persistent challenges in WCIS user engagement, stemming from gaps in design and communication. Many services in SEE adopt top-down approaches with limited user involvement and inadequate educational support. Strengthening participation and promoting transparency in information dissemination are crucial. Tailoring WCIS to specific sectors, such as agriculture, public health, and water management, can help ensure relevance to local needs. Technical challenges remain regarding reliability, trustworthiness and performance of WCIS related to heat- and drought-related impacts. The study concludes with five key recommendations: 1) improve cross-scale engagement, 2) ensure transparency, 3) address sector-specific needs, 4) enhance user-friendliness, and 5) increase reliability and trust.

Practical implications

Extreme heat and drought events are becoming increasingly frequent and severe in Southeastern Europe, exacerbating existing

vulnerabilities in sectors like agriculture, public health, and water management. These climate extremes pose significant challenges for local communities, often leading to negative socio-economic impacts and loss of life. In this study, references to “extreme heat” and “drought” in the survey context are based on

E-mail address: spyros.paparrizos@wur.nl (S. Paparrizos).

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stakeholders' perceptions of elevated temperature and prolonged precipitation deficit, without applying fixed meteorological thresholds. While this framing captures valuable experiential knowledge, it may also reflect varying interpretations shaped by local context, sector, and past experiences

In this context, Weather and Climate Information Services (WCIS) have emerged as vital tools to support adaptation strategies, offering timely, localized information to guide decision-making. However, the effectiveness of WCIS is often hindered by challenges related to accessibility, communication, and user engagement. This study sought to assess the impact and relevance of WCIS in Southeastern Europe, with a focus on extreme heat and drought events, and to identify ways to enhance their utility for local communities.

One of the key findings of the study is the need for increased public awareness and education about climate change and its effects, particularly the risks associated with extreme heat and drought. Understanding the local impacts of climate extremes is crucial for communities to take proactive measures to mitigate risks. Educational campaigns and community outreach initiatives can raise awareness about the increasing likelihood of these events and promote actions such as improved water conservation, heat protection strategies, and adaptive agricultural practices. These efforts should prioritize reaching vulnerable populations, such as the elderly, children, and those in remote areas, who are often the most at risk during extreme weather events.

Another significant implication is the importance of tailoring WCIS to local needs and specific sectors. The study revealed that climate information is often too general or not actionable for end-users, such as farmers or local health authorities. For WCIS to be truly effective, they must be customized to meet the distinct requirements of different sectors. For example, climate services can provide agricultural communities with tailored forecasts on heat and drought patterns, helping them to adjust irrigation schedules, choose more resilient crops, and plan for potential yield losses. Similarly, in public health, climate services can support the creation of heat action plans that protect vulnerable groups during heatwaves, ensuring that response strategies are in place for the most affected areas.

The study also highlights the need for improving the accessibility and usability of WCIS. Many existing services are not easily accessible or understandable to all users, especially those with limited technological skills or literacy. To overcome these barriers, WCIS should be simplified and made available in user-friendly formats. For instance, providing visual representations of climate forecasts, using clear and concise language, and making services available through multiple platforms—such as mobile apps, community radio, and public notice boards—can enhance their reach and effectiveness. Ensuring that climate information is accessible in local languages and formats that suit the needs of diverse populations is essential for promoting wider adoption and use of these services.

A further implication of the study is the importance of ensuring the sustainability of WCIS. The long-term success of these services relies on consistent funding, institutional support, and coordination among relevant stakeholders. For WCIS to remain effective, it is essential to build partnerships between meteorological services, local authorities, and other organizations to share resources, knowledge, and expertise. Regular updates and improvements to climate models and data should be incorporated into service delivery to maintain their relevance and accuracy. Furthermore, fostering local capacity to interpret and use climate information ensures that communities can independently adapt to changing conditions without over-reliance on external sources of support.

Finally, the study stresses the critical need for ongoing investment in data collection and research. Accurate, high-resolution climate data is necessary for improving the reliability of climate predictions, especially for extreme events like heatwaves and droughts. Investments in monitoring systems, data analysis, and

forecasting tools can enhance the precision of climate forecasts, making them more actionable and reliable for decision-making. Additionally, research into climate adaptation strategies, such as the development of drought-resistant crops or urban heat mitigation techniques, is vital for helping communities adapt to the long-term impacts of climate change.

By addressing these practical implications, WCIS can be better positioned to support communities in Southeastern Europe in adapting to extreme heat and drought events. Localized, accessible, and actionable climate information can empower communities to make informed decisions, build resilience, and reduce the impacts of climate extremes. As climate change continues to affect the region, ensuring the effectiveness of WCIS will be crucial in safeguarding vulnerable populations and enhancing overall climate resilience.

1. Introduction

The Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) unequivocally asserted, for the first time, that specific regions in Southern Europe are notably susceptible to heightened risks such as extreme heatwaves, severe droughts, and other extreme weather events (IPCC, 2014). The Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), released in 2023, reinforces these findings, highlighting the increasing vulnerability of Southern Europe to these climatic challenges (IPCC, 2023). While Europe as a whole is vulnerable to climate-related risks, certain regions have been more extensively studied, with their vulnerabilities and adaptation needs better understood (Sutanto et al. 2020; 2025). In contrast, the Balkan region of Southeastern Europe (SEE) has increasingly been identified as a high-risk area for droughts and heatwave events but lacks comprehensive, targeted research on effective adaptation strategies (Paparrizos & Matzarakis, 2016; Klima-vičius & Rimkus, 2023).

In SEE, models predict that in the next decades, the occurrence of extreme heat and drought events will rapidly increase in both frequency and intensity (Sutanto et al., 2020; Douville et al., 2023). In this study, “heat” and “drought” are used in two complementary ways: in the literature review they reflect events characterized in meteorological or climatological terms, while in the survey analysis they refer to stakeholder perceptions of elevated temperature and prolonged precipitation deficit without the application of fixed quantitative thresholds. This perceptual framing is valuable for understanding user experiences and information needs, but it also introduces variability depending on respondents' personal and contextual interpretations (see Lai et al., 2016). These extreme drought and heat events can directly cause significant damage, while their indirect consequences trigger social tension arising from food and water insecurity, along with health problems due to increased heatwaves (Bezák & Mikoš, 2020; Arsenovic et al., 2023; Đurđević et al., 2023; Martínez et al., 2016), prolonged droughts (Stahl et al. 2016; Paparrizos et al. 2018; Sutanto and Van Lanen, 2020; Toreti et al. 2022), compounded events (Mukherjee & Mishra, 2021; Zhang et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2019), possible wildfires occurrence, and loss of biodiversity (Giannaros et al. 2022; Giannaros and Papavasileiou 2023). The risk of drought in eastern and SEE regions have been perceived by water managers increasing, with the highest increase felt in Serbia and small increase felt in Romania (Biella et al., 2024). For instance, the European drought of 2022 was deemed as having severe impacts on terrestrial ecosystem and wildfires in southeast Europe due to its length and other compounding events.

Climate adaptation and resilience strategies are vital in addressing the increasing risks of extreme events and other climate-related impacts. These strategies are designed to support both society and the environment in managing the consequences of climate change (IPCC, 2023), and are widely implemented globally to address the impacts of climate change. Within these adaptation strategies, Weather and Climate

Information Services (hereafter WCIS or simply Climate services) are being increasingly recognized as playing a crucial role (Paparrizos et al. 2021; Street 2016). Weather services, which focus on short-term forecasts, warnings, operational actions, and Climate Services which address longer-term resilience and strategic planning, together enhance adaptation by equipping decision-makers with timely, relevant and usable information under uncertainty. By making weather and climate-related data accessible and actionable, Climate Services strengthen the capacity of institutions and communities to plan and respond effectively (Findlater et al., 2021; Dainelli et al. 2022). In this paper, we use the term *Climate Services* broadly to encompass both weather- and climate-related timescales, while acknowledging their different purposes and user groups. Within the context of climate services, two different types can be distinguished: First-generation climate services are defined as technical sources of scientific information and are primarily aimed at scientific audiences. This generation of WCIS is characterized by a top-down approach as they are created by-and-for the scientists community (Karpouzoglou et al., 2016). In recent years, a more user-oriented, bottom-up approach has been advocated. This interactive approach includes stakeholder engagement and knowledge co-production to ensure that the provided services are tailored to meet the needs of societal users (Vincent et al. 2018; Weichselgartner and Arheimer 2019; Norström et al. 2020; Terrado et al. 2023). Second-generation climate services enhance the quality of information by making it more accurate, context-specific, and aligned with the needs of both users and providers (Di Fant et al. 2024; Paparrizos et al., 2024). These approaches are better able to understand both the practical needs of specific user groups and their key priorities (Georgeson et al., 2017).

Although Climate Services are used as an adaptation strategy to enhance climate-smart decision-making in many European areas, Southeastern Europe, particularly the Balkans, lag behind (Cortekar et al., 2020). This gap is usually due to a combination of factors, including limited access to modern technology, restricted financial resources for infrastructure development, lower awareness of the importance of weather information for agriculture and water management, historical challenges such as political instability, and the geographic complexity of the region (Cortekar et al. 2020).

The aim of this research is to assess the current status and potential of Climate Services to address the impacts of extreme drought and heat in Southeastern Europe (SEE). Specifically, this study examines three interconnected aspects: (1) the status of Weather and Climate

Information Services (WCIS) in the region, reflecting the current awareness, accessibility, and level of trust in these services; (2) the potential of WCIS, defined as their capacity to strengthen climate resilience by making climate information more actionable, accessible, and user-centred; and (3) the barriers and opportunities influencing the effectiveness of WCIS. Barriers may stem from limited resources, knowledge gaps, or infrastructural challenges, while opportunities focus on ways to enhance service uptake—such as through improved communication, targeted educational initiatives, and tailored hazard warnings. Understanding these interrelated factors will provide insights into how WCIS should be implemented to better support adaptation and resilience strategies in SEE, addressing regional needs amid increasing climate risks.

2. Study area, methods and data

The focus of this study is on ten countries in Southeastern Europe, including the countries of Slovenia (SI), Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA), Croatia (HR), Serbia (RS), Montenegro (ME), Albania (AL), North Macedonia (MK), Romania (RO), Bulgaria (BG), and Greece (GR) (Fig. 1).

The research design was based on a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods. Firstly, a bibliometric analysis was conducted to quantitatively evaluate current research areas in the domain of WCIS in Europe on heat and drought. Additionally, it was used to highlight the research gap in Southeast Europe relative to other regions in Europe. In addressing Southeastern Europe's status as a climate change hotspot, the methodology involves prioritizing the development of accessible and scientifically rigorous WCIS. This approach aims to enhance comprehension of the scientific dimensions of climate change within the region and deepen the understanding of the scientific aspects of climate change.

Secondly, market research was performed to identify the current WCIS providers, as well as the current and potential demand for WCIS in SEE. Thirdly, a survey was developed, to collect insights from the general public around the theme of WCIS for heat and drought adaptation. This was complemented with semi-structured interviews with key informants of heat and drought extremes. The research design for this study was structured to provide a comprehensive and multifaceted analysis of WCIS in SEE. By combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the study seeks to gather diverse data sources and

Fig. 1. Geographic Locations of the study area in Southeastern Europe: Slovenia (SI), Croatia (HR), Bosnia and Herzegovina (BA), Serbia (RS), Montenegro (ME), North Macedonia (MK), Albania (AL), Greece (EL), Bulgaria (BG), and Romania (RO).

perspectives. This holistic approach aims to offer valuable insights into the current state of WCIS utilization, barriers to implementation, and opportunities for improvement. The findings from this research will contribute to inform efforts to design WCIS that can provide actionable recommendations to enhance resilience and climate adaptation in the face of droughts and heatwaves affecting the SEE region. The following sections provide more information on the various research approaches adopted in the current study.

2.1. Bibliometric analysis on heat and drought extremes and climate services in SEE

To better understand the research gap in WCIS development in SEE a bibliometric analysis was performed, following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA, Moher et al., 2016, Fig. 2). The search focused on climate extremes related topics, specifically heat and drought events (Fig. 2a) and the WCIS status in SEE (Fig. 2b). PRISMA approach was selected due to its completeness and usefulness in assessing the literature in relation to climate change (e.g. Paparrizos et al. 2023; Lindawati & Meiryani, 2024). PRISMA, originally intended for systematic reviews in medical and health sciences, offers a structured framework that prioritizes transparency and methodological rigor. This framework can be effectively applied to bibliometric analysis and literature reviews across various disciplines. By following PRISMA guidelines, researchers can systematically and rigorously synthesize bibliometric data, thereby bolstering the reliability and credibility of

their research outcomes (Baidya & Saha, 2024).

Similarly, the bibliometric review was conducted using the keywords “ (“climate services“ OR “climate information services“) AND (“Albania“ OR “Bosnia and Herzegovina“ OR “Bulgaria“ OR “Croatia“ OR “Greece“ OR “Kosovo“ OR “Montenegro“ OR “North Macedonia“ OR “Romania“ OR “Serbia“ OR “Slovenia“)” to assess the current state of research in the field of climate information services in Europe. The search gave the result of 47 documents that were further filtered based using the same criteria as for the weather and climate extremes (Fig. 2b).

To manipulate the data more efficiently, the complete bibliographic data for both searches, were exported in the BibTeX (.bib) file format. Biblioshiny R software packages have been used as bibliometric analysis tools for summarising the results (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). Biblioshiny is highly recommended for scientific mapping, offering comprehensive research capabilities in bibliometrics and scientometrics. It features an intuitive interface along with a diverse array of functions, analyses, and graphical representations (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).

2.2. Market research on climate service providers in SEE

The fmarket analysis focused on collecting and qualitatively assessing available market data to determine the current and potential demand for Climate Services in SEE. The objective was to identify the types of WCIS services available, the providers offering them, and their relevance for supporting climate-smart decision making. Given the limited existing research on WCIS in SEE, this step was essential to establish an

Fig. 2. PRISMA framework shows literature search criteria for climate extremes in Southeastern Europe of the current study. a) Search focus on climate extremes, specially droughts and heatwaves and b) focus on the WCIS in SEE. The used terms of part a) include: (“climate extremes” OR “extreme weather events” OR “climatic extremes”) AND (“Southeast Europe” OR Balkans OR “Balkan Peninsula” OR Serbia OR Greece OR Albania OR Bulgaria OR “North Macedonia” OR “Slovenia” OR “Bosnia and Herzegovina” OR “Croatia” OR “Montenegro” OR “Romania”, while for part b) these include: (“climate services” OR “climate information services”) AND (“Albania” OR “Bosnia and Herzegovina” OR “Bulgaria” OR “Croatia” OR “Greece” OR “Kosovo” OR “Montenegro” OR “North Macedonia” OR “Romania” OR “Serbia” OR “Slovenia”). The Web of Science platform (WOS) was used to perform the search with the terms (“climate extremes” OR “extreme weather events” OR “climatic extremes”) AND (“Southeast Europe” OR Balkans OR “Balkan Peninsula” OR Serbia OR Greece OR Albania OR Bulgaria OR “North Macedonia” OR “Slovenia” OR “Bosnia and Herzegovina” OR “Croatia” OR “Montenegro” OR “Romania”). The search yielded 201 documents for the period 1999–2024 (Fig. 2a). After screening, 22 articles were excluded due to publication year (which was older than 1999), language (not written in English), and document type (only articles and reviews were included in the current search).

initial regional overview. We identified 37 key WCIS providers across SEE, mapping them by country and by the sectors they serve. Information was also gathered on relevant stakeholders-such as local communities, government agencies, and industry groups- to understand the broader service landscape and potential user base.

2.3. Survey description

To explore public awareness, experiences, and needs related to weather and climate information services (WCIS) for heat and drought adaptation in Southeast Europe (SEE), we conducted a qualitative study based on an online survey targeting citizens in the region. The questionnaire was open from January to March 2024 and was disseminated through email lists, social media platforms, and the ClearClimate project network (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131220>). Given the diverse dissemination channels, the total number of individuals reached could not be determined, and therefore no response rate is reported. To enhance accessibility, the survey was made available in English, Serbian, and Greek. Its structure and process was adapted from existing studies on climate services (Lambrechts et al., 2024) and tailored to capture citizen-level perspectives. The survey aimed to assess general awareness and current use of WCIS, understand how these services are perceived in relation to recent extreme heat and drought events, identify barriers to their uptake, and gather suggestions for improving their accessibility and relevance. A total of 60 responses were collected, and further details on the survey design and respondent characteristics are provided in Annex 1.

2.4. Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with nine (9) academic experts from Southeastern Europe. These experts, identified through the ClearClimate project network (but not directly related to the project) and using a snowball effect approach, have various fields of expertise related to hydrology, physical geography, meteorology, and climatology. The interviews were designed to gather more in-depth perspectives on several key areas concerning experiences with heat and drought, impact on local communities and perceptions about weather

and climate information services now and in the future. The respondents' extensive experience and profound understanding of these subjects allowed them to significantly contribute to the current research. The interviews, conducted online via MS Teams, gathered in-depth information on their experiences with extreme heat and drought events, the impacts on local communities and societal sectors, and their perceptions about the future of Climate Services for heat and drought adaptation in SEE.

3. Results

3.1. Bibliometric analysis on heat and drought events in SEE

The number of publications about extreme events, especially drought and heat, are rising. The sharpest rise is seen from the 2017 and the highest number is observed in 2022. A detailed overview of the bibliometric analysis results can be found in Annex 2.

The 179 articles in our collection include 1582 authors from 20 countries. There are 5 single authored articles. The annual growth rate in the number of articles in 10.5 %. A co-authors ratio per document is 9.9, with international co-authorship of 42.6 %. These numbers indicate trends towards multi-authored articles, and inter- and transdisciplinary collaborations. Even though the trends suggest rise in the internationalisation, the majority of articles come from the region of SEE.

The analysis identified 678 unique keywords with *precipitation*, *variability*, *trends*, *climate extremes* and *temperature* being among the most frequent (Fig. 3). Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 3, keywords evolved over time. The co-occurrence of terms indicates instances where two keywords often appear together in multiple manuscripts (Fig. 4a). By analysing these co-occurrences, we can identify emerging trends and key areas of focus during different research periods, which highlight shifts in the popularity of various research topics (Radhakrishnan et al., 2017). Additionally, co-occurrence analysis of the keywords structure was utilized to uncover major thematic clusters. The co-occurrence network and word cloud analysis indicate that research on extremes in SEE predominantly focuses on trends in indices and physical drivers, rather than on adaptation and climate change mitigation strategies. According to Li et al. (2021), climate and environmental sciences dominated as the

Fig. 3. Keywords evolution over time. Results from the bibliometric analysis on heat and drought extremes and Climate Services in SEE of the current study.

Fig. 4. A) keywords evolution over time and b) their co-occurrences found in the bibliometric analysis of the current study.

primary research areas. Additionally, keyword burst analysis (Fig. 4b) highlighted emerging research directions, including changes in atmospheric rivers, the effects of global nitrogen content on extreme weather, and the interconnections between water quality, soil moisture, and extreme weather events. Similarly, Ng (2024) showed that the field has expanded significantly over the past two decades, with five major research themes emerging: *global impacts and policy*, *agricultural adaptation*, *extreme weather and prediction*, *risk management*, and *heat waves and human health*. Additionally, six international collaboration clusters were recognized, encompassing the Asia-Pacific group, central and southern European group, northern European group, low-latitude countries, small countries, and African countries.

3.2. Market analysis of climate service providers in Southeast Europe

The market analysis identified 37 WCIS providers across SEE, present in every country of the region. Fig. 5 summarizes the geographical distribution of these services (panel a) and their provision status (b). In this context, ‘status’ refers to whether services are fully funded by public sources, supported by a mix of public and other partners, or sustained through collaboration with private actors, EU programmes, or other funding streams. Distinguishing between these provision models helps to illustrate the different institutional and financial arrangements through which WCIS are delivered.

Serbia and Slovenia have the highest number of WCIS providers addressing weather and climate extremes (seven each), followed by Bosnia and Herzegovina (five) and Croatia (four) (Fig. 5a). Compared to Cortekar et al. (2020), who reported a much more limited number of

providers, our analysis suggests that the landscape in SEE is broader and more diverse than previously documented. Pure public funding remains the predominant model for providing WCIS, with 59.5 % services being operated or financed through this type of funding (Fig. 5b). The remaining 40.5 % of WCIS providers operate through joint funding scheme between public, private, or other sources. Although many WCIS providers issue information relevant to heat and drought, only a small subset explicitly focusses on these hazards. National meteorological and hydrological services (NMHS) remain the primary issuing authorities for related warnings, disseminating them via official portals and social media, and indirectly- through news media. This ensures relatively wide and timely access, but also highlights opportunities to expand specialized offerings for these particular extremes.

Fig. 6 highlights the diversity of WCIS information in SEE in terms of sectoral scope and temporal coverage. While agriculture, water management, energy, transportation, and health are the most frequently addressed sectors (Fig. 6a), many services are designed for broad applicability rather than a single user group. This breadth supports multiple decision-making contexts, but can make it harder for users with highly specific needs –such as targeted heatwave or drought risk information; to locate the most relevant outputs.

Temporal cover also varies: 29,3% of providers use historical data to assess climate extremes, 22,4% focus on short-term weather forecasts (daily to weekly), and 48,3% provide long-term climate outlooks (seasonal to decadal scales) (Fig. 6b). Seasonal forecasts often linked to drought risk management are used by 27.6 % of providers, while short-term forecasts play a more prominent role in heatwave-related services. This variety of time horizons reflects both the multiple user needs across

Fig. 5. The number of (a) Weather and Climate Information Service providers, and (b) their provision status in southeast Europe.

Fig. 6. Sectors for which the identified services provide information (a), and temporal scale of weather and climate services (b) in Southeast Europe (SEE). S2D stands for seasonal to decadal predictions.

the region and the differing capacities of providers, underscoring the importance of aligning service design with intended applications.

3.3. Perceptions and responses to extreme heat and drought events in SEE

3.3.1. Participant demographics and interview overview

A total of 60 online survey responses were obtained from January to March 2024 through Google forms. Due to the option to skip certain questions, some answers had fewer responses. Additionally, some participants with original nationality outside the selected study area, but who work with the countries of interest, were included in the survey. The participant demographics revealed a majority of women (55 %) compared to men (45 %), spanning various age categories from under 20 to over 60, with the largest cohorts in the 20–30 (30 %) and 30–40 (28 %) age brackets (Appendix Fig. 3.1 and 3.2). Most participants were from Greece (66.6 %), representing a diverse range of occupations, with Research and Science constituting the largest group (31 %), closely followed by students (25 %) (Appendix Fig. 3.3 and 3.4). While the demographic distribution of responses reflects the varying levels of engagement and accessibility achieved during the survey period, it also mirrors the differences in existing WCIS networks and active stakeholder communities across the region. This context is important for interpreting the results, as certain countries are more strongly represented in the dataset. A comprehensive overview of the demographic profiles of the respondents is available in Annex 3.

The survey results were complemented by semi-structured interviews with a total of nine academics from various Southeast European countries and diverse research fields. Most of the participants were from Serbia (six), followed by Hungary but working in Serbia (two), and Greece (one). Annex 4 provides details on the interviews conducted, including the country of origin, title, and working fields of the participants. The remaining information, such as names and contact details, has been anonymized for privacy reasons. The results and narratives presented in the following sections combine the survey data and insights from the key informant interviews, including graphical representations of survey results alongside quotes and key points from the interviews. It is important to note that the demographic profile of respondents indicates a relatively high representation of scientists and students. While this may introduce a bias in perspectives toward academic and research-oriented viewpoints, it also reflects the accessibility of respondents through existing professional and educational networks in the region. As

this study adopts an exploratory approach, the survey was not designed as a representative sample of all stakeholder groups but rather as an initial scoping exercise to capture perceptions and experiences across accessible communities. This limitation is acknowledged, and the findings should therefore be interpreted with caution, particularly when generalizing to specific stakeholder groups. Nonetheless, these results provide valuable insights into the awareness, concerns, and knowledge gaps that exist within active knowledge communities, which can inform the design of more targeted and inclusive stakeholder engagement in future research.

3.3.2. Severity perception, concern, experience and preparedness on heat and drought extremes

In line with observations and model projections that indicate an increase in extreme heat and drought events in SEE, survey participants and expert interviewees also anticipate an increase in the frequency and intensity of these events. Fig. 7 depicts the perception of severity of extreme heat and drought events among the survey participants, which is confirmed by a large part of interviewees (>80 %) who assessed the severity of extreme heat and drought as “significant” or “extremely severe”. Heat was more frequently considered as “extremely severe” compared to drought (Fig. 6). Interestingly, responses across different countries – such as Greece and Serbia – show similar severity ratings for heat and drought, suggesting a regionally shared concern about these extremes. This similarity indicates that, although the survey data may not be fully representative across SEE, perceptions of climate severity appear consistent, possibly reflecting common experiences or awareness of these growing climate risks across the region.

Survey participants were asked to indicate on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 the level of concern about heat and drought extremes, whether they have had prior experience with these events, as well as how prepared they currently feel against future heat and drought extreme events. Fig. 8 presents their responses.

Fig. 8a indicates that respondents feel “very much” to “extremely concerned” about occurring heat and drought extremes affecting their respective regions and communities. Many respondents also have prior experience on extreme drought and heatwave events (Fig. 8b). Although they have a high concern and experience in extreme droughts and heatwaves, only a few of them are prepared and extremely prepared (Fig. 8c). Most respondents indicated that they personally have a very low level of perceived preparedness (average = 2.6).

Fig. 7. Severity assessment (in percentage) of extreme heat and drought events in SEE (results from the survey, n = 60).

Fig. 8. Level of concern (a), prior experience (b), and level of preparedness (c) about heat and drought extreme events of survey participants. Results were calculated on a Likert scale from 1 to 5.

Next, respondents were asked to indicate the effectiveness of various WCIS elements coping with future heat and drought extreme events. Fig. 9 illustrates the respondents' perceived effectiveness of short-term weather forecasts (a), seasonal to decadal (S2D) predictions (b), communication and warnings (c), and educational programs around heat and drought extremes (d).

Based on the results, study participants find short-term weather forecasts, seasonal to decadal predictions, and prior communication and warnings very effective (mean 3.4) for adapting to extreme heat and drought events (Figs. 9a, b, and c, respectively). However, perceptions of educational programs on heat and drought adaptation differ. With a lower average response (mean 3.2) and greater variation (Fig. 9d), participants expressed uncertainty about their usefulness, noting that while educational programs might be helpful for specific groups—like farmers or elderly citizens—most people feel they already know what actions to take during extreme events. Instead, they prioritize receiving timely forecasts and alerts on when these events will occur. Interviews further revealed that educational programs in Southeastern Europe,

which are often delivered through a top-down governmental approach, face trust issues among the public. Many respondents expressed limited confidence in their government's handling of climate-related information, stating that these programs are sometimes perceived as disconnected from the immediate needs of communities. Some interviewees also pointed out that governmental media regulations often limit the availability and neutrality of information, with climate adaptation topics receiving lower priority in public agendas. As a result, educational programs may lack appeal and effectiveness. To better support communities, these programs should focus on building trust by delivering reliable, actionable information that addresses local concerns and offers practical steps for adaptation.

3.4. Mapping the effects of extreme heat and drought on socio-economic and environmental systems

Based on the results from the surveys and interviews, it is perceived that heatwaves and droughts have significant consequences across all

Fig. 9. Perceived effectiveness of various Weather and Climate Information Service elements towards heat and drought adaptation: short-term weather forecasts (a), seasonal to decadal (S2D) predictions, communication and warnings (c), and educational programs (d). Results were calculated on a Likert scale from 1 to 5.

SEE countries. Agriculture is profoundly impacted, with issues such as the spread of exotic or invasive species, increased water demand, and soil degradation being prominent (Fiala et al., 2014; Fabri et al., 2022). Immediate threats include yield reductions and crop losses due to escalating heat and drought extremes (Sutanto et al., 2024). Indirect consequences, such as reduced production and lower yields, exacerbate food insecurity, leading to elevated food prices and economic instability, particularly affecting small-scale farmers and vulnerable populations in SEE. Given that droughts and heatwaves have tremendous impacts on agriculture, many WCIS in SEE are aimed to cope with these issues (see Fig. 6a).

Changing climate patterns also affect water sources and infrastructure. Prolonged hydro-meteorological droughts resulting from decreased precipitation and increased evaporation lead to water shortages (Van Loon, 2015). This situation is critical in SEE, where water is essential for hydropower production, impacting energy generation, especially during peak electricity demand for cooling.

Excessive energy consumption during heatwaves can trigger power blackouts, as it was mentioned by several study participants. Furthermore, heat and drought can degrade water quality, affecting both ecological habitats like lakes and rivers and the safety of drinking water (Wright et al., 2014). These challenges underscore the need for sustainable water management and resilient infrastructure.

Additionally, heatwaves and droughts pose significant health risks, particularly for vulnerable groups such as the elderly, children, and outdoor workers (Di Napoli et al., 2018). Health issues including heatstroke, dehydration, respiratory illnesses, and vector-borne diseases are exacerbated during prolonged periods of extreme heat and water scarcity. Previous studies have already shown increased mortality and

hospitalization in Serbia during hot summer months (Arsenović et al., 2023; Savić et al., 2023) and several participants also noted a notable increase in mortality rates during these periods.

Following insights from interviews and surveys, a mind map (Fig. 10) has been developed to visually represent the effects of heat and drought in SEE across various sectors and their associated consequences.

4. Principles for enhancing the use of climate services for heat and drought adaptation in SEE

This study highlights the important role of Weather and Climate Information Services (WCIS) in supporting adaptation and building resilience to the increased heat and drought extremes in Southeast Europe (SEE). It is important to remind that, throughout this work, references to “heat” and “drought” denote general conditions of elevated temperature and prolonged precipitation deficits as perceived by stakeholders, rather than strictly defined meteorological or climatological events. This qualitative framing reflects the nature of the survey and interview data, which capture subjective experiences and perceptions rather than quantitative thresholds or objective meteorological characterizations. As such, the findings provide valuable insights into user needs and engagement with WCIS, but should be interpreted with an understanding of their perceptual limitations and geographic variability across the SEE region. Moreover, while WCIS are relevant across a wide spectrum of stakeholders — from policymakers and sectoral experts to citizens and local communities — this study examined them in a general sense without systematically differentiating between groups. We acknowledge this as a limitation, but it also reflects the cross-sectoral nature of WCIS, which are inherently designed to serve multiple audiences. The

Fig. 10. Mind map depicting the effects and consequences of extreme heat and drought events in SEE based on the results of the current study.

principles proposed below directly address this by emphasizing that WCIS must always be tailored to the specific decision-making context and the needs of the intended users.

Despite the significant volume of climate services in SEE (see Fig. 5a), many currently operate in a predominantly top-down manner with limited user involvement. The evidence from this study's surveys of WCIS users and climate extreme experts suggests a pressing need to enhance the coverage, accuracy, and tailoring of these services to improve their effectiveness for climate adaptation. In response, we propose five key principles that are visualized in Fig. 11 to guide the further development and uptake of WCIS for heat and drought adaptation in SEE.

4.1. Community engagement, education, and awareness

A central theme emerging from the data is the variable awareness and understanding of climate change and related WCIS among communities. This mixed interest in educational programs reflects broader gaps in climate literacy across SEE, which limit proactive engagement with heat and drought adaptation. Enhancing community engagement through targeted education and awareness-raising (for example in schools, local community centres, agricultural extension programs, and public health campaigns) is therefore essential to foster climate resilience against heat and drought extremes (Baiardi and Morana 2021; Pekez et al. 2024). Our findings suggest that integrating climate change adaptation topics into school curricula could address significant

knowledge gaps identified among young people –for example as documented in Serbia (Lešćešen et al. 2024). These efforts should be complemented by practical, experimental learning such as field trips and exercises that demonstrate the real-world relevance of WCIS. Given mistrust in government authorities highlighted by respondents, bottom-up initiatives developed in cooperation with local educational institutions may be more effective. For broader public engagement, campaigns tailored to diverse audiences are critical to improving understanding of how WCIS can help mitigate the impacts of heat and drought extremes. These efforts should recognise the diverse socio-cultural contexts within SEE and address perceptual differences in how heat and drought are experienced and understood (Lai et al. 2016). Increasing public climate literacy builds a foundation for greater acceptance and use of WCIS, thereby supporting more informed and climate-smart decision-making.

4.2. Transparency of information

Transparency in the development and dissemination of Weather and Climate Information Services (WCIS) is critical for building user trust and promoting informed decision-making, particularly for complex phenomena such as heatwaves and droughts. Promoting transparency involves clearly communicating the data sources, analytical methods, and uncertainties associated with the provided heatwave and drought information. For instance, explaining how temperature thresholds for heatwaves or precipitation deficits for droughts are determined

Fig. 11. Key principles for enhancing and fostering the further development and provision of WCIS in SEE for adaptation to extreme heat and drought events. The figure presents generic principles applicable across multiple sectors, stakeholder groups, and temporal scales; detailed guidance is provided in the text.

—whether through meteorological standards or local impact thresholds—helps users contextualize the severity and reliability of heatwave forecasts or the accuracy of drought predictions. This is especially important given that stakeholders’ understanding and trust in WCIS depend heavily on their awareness of how information is generated and its associated limitations. Moreover, fostering open communication channels between WCIS providers and users enables feedback and collaborative refinement of services, aligning with the principles of co-production (Vincent et al. 2018; Norström et al. 2020;). Such engagement is essential to tailor information to user needs and build trust, particularly when service accuracy can be influenced by regional climate variability and model uncertainties ((Sutanto and Van Lanen, 2021)). Given the uneven geographic representation and perceptual biases identified in this study, transparency should also include contextualizing forecasts within local climate realities and user experiences. Clear disclosure of the confidence levels and potential limitations of WCIS information—especially for complex and variable phenomena like heatwaves and droughts—will empower users to make better-informed adaptation decisions. Finally, transparency can be enhanced through case studies and examples demonstrating how WCIS have effectively supported adaptation, providing tangible evidence of benefits that help overcome skepticism and institutional barriers. While transparency requires clear communication of analytical methods, data sources, and uncertainties, this can sometimes result in complex and technical information that may be difficult for some users to interpret. Finding a balance between transparency and usability is therefore essential. WCIS should provide sufficient methodological detail and context for those who need it (e.g., researchers, technical experts, policymakers), while simultaneously translating key messages into simplified, actionable formats for broader audiences. Approaches such as

tiered communication, visual summaries, and user-focused guidance can help reconcile these potentially conflicting objectives, ensuring that services remain both trustworthy and accessible.

4.3. Tailoring information to the local needs

This principle highlights the importance of tailoring Climate Services to the specific contexts and needs of local communities and users. Since the impacts of heatwaves and droughts vary widely across SEE (Biella et al., 2024), WCIS must provide locally relevant, actionable information rather than generic outputs. Hence, there is a necessity to customize WCIS to meet the diverse user needs, as one size does not fit all. Different sectors, such as agriculture, water management, and public health, require distinct types of data and thresholds to guide effective decisions. Farmers and agricultural experts, for example, offer valuable insights into how temperature extremes and water deficit impact crop growth, livestock health, and overall farm operations. Their practical knowledge is invaluable for identifying critical climate thresholds and adapting agricultural practices to sustain productivity. Similarly, public health stakeholders help define heat indices and thermal comfort levels that reflect vulnerability patterns in specific communities (Xu et al., 2016). This user-driven input ensures that WCIS outputs are not only scientifically robust but also tailored to real-world decision contexts. Beyond sectoral differences, WCIS also need to account for the decision-making level, ranging from high-level policymakers and municipal planners to farmers and individual citizens. Each group requires information in a different form and at a different level of detail. Recognizing this diversity reinforces the importance of tailoring services to both the sectoral and societal context. To enhance operational relevance, WCIS development should move beyond generic calls for “user tailoring”

toward co-creating protocols with end-users that specify thresholds, information formats, and decision support tools aligned with sectoral and local priorities. This would reduce ambiguity and increase the likelihood that services are actionable, relevant, and widely adopted.

4.4. Improved accessibility through user-friendly services

The fourth principle emphasizes the need to improve accessibility of WCIS for heat and drought extremes by ensuring services are user-friendly and cater to the diverse needs and circumstances of different societal user groups, including those with limited illiteracy or technical skills. Achieving user-friendliness does not imply compromising transparency. Rather, effective WCIS must manage the trade-off between providing comprehensive, technically detailed information and delivering simplified, actionable messages tailored to different user groups. Strategies such as layered information presentation, contextual explanations, and visual or audio aids can help ensure that essential uncertainty and methodological information is communicated without overwhelming end-users. While information on heatwaves and droughts is often available, our findings confirm that much of this data remains complex or technical, which limits its practical use for many end-users. This gap is further amplified by the subjective and qualitative nature of the survey, reflecting varied user experiences and understandings of what constitutes extreme heat or drought in their local context. To address this challenge, WCIS providers should simplify the communication of heat and drought information, using clear language, visual aids, and where appropriate, audio formats to broaden accessibility (e.g., see Kumar et al., 2021). Recognizing the qualitative differences in users' perception and interpretation of climate extremes, services should adopt flexible dissemination approaches that resonate with local knowledge and cultural norms. Additionally, improving accessibility means delivering information in local languages and tailoring outreach to specific regions and communities most affected by heatwaves and drought risks. Multi-channel dissemination is critical—leveraging both digital platforms and traditional media such as community radio or printed materials—to reach audiences with varying access to technology. By embedding accessibility and usability into WCIS design, providers can ensure that weather and climate information on heat and drought extremes is more inclusive and better understood, and more readily applied by all users regardless of their technical proficiency or socioeconomic background. Such user-centred services will enhance adaptation capacities, especially for vulnerable populations, by transforming subjective experiences and qualitative insights into actionable knowledge.

4.5. Reliability and trust

The implementation of WCIS in Southeast Europe is influenced by various institutional barriers, which have direct implications for the effectiveness and acceptance of these services in the region. These barriers are forming crucial considerations for policymakers and researchers aiming to understand why WCIS adoption lags behind and how policy measures can help overcome these hurdles (Wanner & Pröbstl-Haider, 2019; Cortekar et al., 2020). Ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of WCIS is essential for building user confidence and increasing the uptake of information, particularly in the context of heat and drought extremes. Our findings show that concerns over forecast reliability are not only technical but also shaped by the subjective and qualitative nature of users' experiences. Survey responses reflected personal interpretations of "heatwaves" and "droughts," which may differ from meteorological definitions, and this variation should be acknowledged when assessing service performance across the region. Combined with the uneven representation of countries in the sample, these factors suggest caution when generalising findings, but they also highlight the need for WCIS providers to communicate clearly how extreme events are defined and measured.

Study participants expressed specific concerns about the reliability of forecasts during heatwaves and droughts, highlighting the need for continuous improvement and rigorous quality assurance measures tailored to these conditions. Transparent communication about the methodologies used, the criteria for defining extreme events, and the limitations of WCIS, as discussed in previous sections, is vital for maintaining trust. Including verification metrics or user-oriented performance indicators could further strengthen confidence and demonstrate accountability. By providing clear, accurate, and timely information about heatwaves and droughts, governments and institutions can enhance their credibility and foster public cooperation. Building trust in WCIS also involves demonstrating the tangible benefits of these services through case studies and success stories, showing how accurate forecasts and timely information have helped mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events (Sutanto and Van Lanen, 2024). Tailoring such examples to local contexts and linking them to measurable adaptation outcomes could further enhance relevance and trust. Engaging with local communities to gather feedback and address their concerns can strengthen the relationship between WCIS providers and users. Overall, building reliability and trust therefore depends not only on technical accuracy but also on engaging distinct user groups with approaches suited to their roles—for example, ensuring that political decision-makers receive strategic long-term assessments, while citizens and practitioners have access to timely and actionable information for immediate adaptation needs. Building trust in WCIS depends on both technical accuracy and the ability to communicate information in ways that are understandable and actionable for different user groups, highlighting the importance of reconciling transparency with usability. Adaptation to climate change is fundamentally a matter of governance (Termeer et al., 2017). Therefore, a coordinated effort involving governments, institutions, and local communities is crucial to overcoming institutional barriers and enhancing the effectiveness of WCIS. By fostering a collaborative environment and ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of WCIS, Southeast Europe can better prepare for and respond to the challenges posed by heatwaves and droughts.

5. Conclusions

This study highlights the critical importance of WCIS in enhancing climate resilience and adaptation to extreme heat and drought events in SEE. By employing a comprehensive mixed-methods approach, combining bibliometric analysis, market research, surveys, and semi-structured interviews, the research provides valuable insights into the current landscape and future potential of WCIS in the region. The bibliometric analysis and market research reveal a diverse but fragmented WCIS provider landscape across SEE, with a notable gap in specialized focus on extreme heat and drought events. While the number of providers is increasing, many services still lack targeted information tailored to these critical risks. National meteorological and hydrological services remain central actors, yet their warnings tend to be general and are not consistently communicated effectively to the public. Survey results and interviews reveal that both the general public and academic experts perceive extreme heat and drought as severe and escalating threats. Despite frequent personal exposure to these events, there is a widespread sense of insufficient preparedness, highlighting the need for more locally tailored and accessible information that addresses specific sectoral and community needs. While short-term forecasts and seasonal predictions are valued, opportunities exist to improve educational outreach and awareness about climate extremes. To address these challenges, this study proposes several key principles for enhancing WCIS: increase community engagement and education, promoting transparency, tailoring information to local contextual needs, improving accessibility, and building reliability and trust. Implementing these principles can improve the effectiveness of WCIS in supporting adaptive decision-making, thereby contributing to enhanced climate resilience across SEE. Although progress has been made in expanding WCIS

in SEE, focused efforts are still required to enhance their relevance, usability and impact on heat and drought adaptation. A critical dimension of this effort is recognizing both the temporal and societal diversity of WCIS. Weather services provide short-term forecasts and warnings for immediate action, while climate services support longer-term planning and resilience strategies. At the same time, WCIS serve multiple user groups — from policymakers and sectoral experts to local stakeholders and citizens — each requiring information in different forms and levels of detail. Tailoring services to these timescales and audiences is essential to ensure that WCIS are both actionable and trusted. A collaborative, multi-level stakeholder approach is essential to foster the development of more responsive and actionable climate services, ultimately strengthening the region's resilience and capacity to adapt to a changing climate.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Spyridon Paparrizos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dragan Milošević:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Zorica Podračanin:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Tim Friso Lode-wijk:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Raffaele Vignola:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Samuel J. Sutanto:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Maria del Pozo Garcia:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Wouter J. Smolenaars:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Miroslav Vujčić:** Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Gordana Kranjac-Berisavljevic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Biljana Basarin:** Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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